

Insight4EO: Disaster Management in Real Time

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Integrating Earth Observation (EO) products onto spacecraft opens new application possibilities, with data prioritization techniques conserving bandwidth and power, and emergency management solutions offering timely alerts. However, challenges arise in accessing L1/L2 data and creating an efficient execution environment. Insight4EO addresses these with optimized L1/L2 product designed for onboard processing of both Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and optical payloads, and a versatile multi-application environment using Multi-Processor and FPGA technology. Demonstrated by an extreme weather application, Insight4EO facilitates efficient EO processing onboard spacecraft for disaster management in real time.

1 Introduction

Based on the 2022 International Labour Organization Report [1], a 24-hour notice can lead to 30% decrease in natural disaster-related deaths. Knowing this, it is clear that early warning plays a vital role in disaster management, where real time Earth Observation (EO) applications could detect incidences in the early stages or even before they have started.

In the last years, due to this and other EO applications, the increase of EO data has proposed significant challenges for the traditional satellite data pipeline due to bandwidth limitations and storage constraints.

Artificial intelligence (AI) offers a promising solution by enabling faster and smarter data processing in EO applications [2]. AI executed onboard spacecraft presents novel applications, such as onboard image quality assessment and low-latency data availability for emergencies. However, integrating AI into EO data processing faces challenges like accessing Level 1 (L1) and Level 2 (L2) data and creating suitable software/hardware (SW/HW) environments due to low-power available in on-board computers.

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Figure 1: L1/L2 Product Generation over a Deimos-2 RGB image. Top-left: Raw data; top-right: radiometrically processed data. Bottom-left: Results after geometric processing; bottom-right: Results of the sea-land mask extraction.

Insight4EO emerges as a solution addressing these limitations, offering low-latency algorithms for onboard data generation and efficient processing environments for AI applications in real time, under 5 minutes.

Insight4EO is a flexible and modular product line available both as an integrated HW/SW solution and as a stand-alone SW solution (Fig. 2), offering a plug-and-play pre-qualified solution to partner units (e.g., iDRS for communications and the full suite of optical payloads from Dragonfly [3]). This differentiates Insight4EO from similar products which appear to be linked to specific onboard processing HW solutions [4–6], are restricted to certain payloads [7], or on the contrary tend to focus on SW only [8].

Insight4EO is supported by Deimos' MLOps framework, which facilitates easy deployment of third-party apps and seamless integration between ground and flight capabilities within the Deimos EO processing ecosystem, being able to process optical and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) payloads, and being of particular interest for EO applications in disaster management.

Being a TRL 9 product, Insight4EO will be in service in the CASSINI mission of ISIS and it is already commercially available to be used in satellites.

2 Insight4EO Overview

Insight4EO emerges as a versatile platform adaptable for integrated HW/SW or standalone SW deployment, furnishing optimized L1/L2 products for SAR and optical payloads. It fosters a multi-application processing environment leveraging Multi-Processor and FPGA technologies, empowering Machine Learning (ML) and AI applications. Insight4EO facilitates low-latency, high-quality EO product generation, supporting various applications and integrating third-party AI tools within the Deimos EO processing ecosystem. The SW framework encompasses four key features:

- **L1/L2 Product Generation:** Derives EO products from raw satellite payload and onboard computer data, supporting real-time services for SAR and optical payloads, including multi-spectral and hyperspectral configurations; see Figure 1.
- **EO Applications:** Manages insight extraction from L1/L2 products, offering Data Prioritization for assessing data relevance and Information Retrieval for object detection and classification, tailored for Land, Maritime, and Weather Services. Third-party apps integration allows users to deploy their analytics tools.
- **Data Services:** Handles data transfers, compression, encryption, and packetization for efficient product transmission, ensuring priority products are promptly delivered through re-configurable data handling.
- **Re-planning and Tasking:** Enhances onboard autonomy with real-time re-tasking for short-term observation redirection and tip and cue functionality for inter-satellite data utilization. Onboard Flight Dynamics support autonomous orbit determination and prediction.
- **MLOps:** Enables Continuous Integration and Continuous Deploying (CI/CD) during flight, ensuring the models remain mission relevant and minimizing performance drift.

However, applying ML/AI techniques to EO data onboard spacecraft introduces challenges. EO applications typically rely on processed L1/L2 data, posing a domain gap between training and test data. Insight4EO mitigates this issue by providing L1/L2 processing on board. For optical payloads, Insight4EO involves the following processing steps: **L1A** processing prepares raw image data by adding essential metadata. This includes time calibration, which assigns timestamps to each image line, pixel flagging to identify defective pixels, and geolocation to determine the coordinates of image pixels. Next, **L1B** processing focuses on correcting pixel-level image data for radiometric accuracy. It begins with relative calibration to ensure homogeneity between pixels, followed by equalization to further refine pixel responses. Cosmetic filling replaces defective pixels, while denoising improves the signal-to-noise ratio and deconvolution reduces blurring. The original values of defective pixels are then restored through cosmetic restoration. Absolute calibration converts pixel intensity to radiance, and finally, band-to-band registration aligns pixels across different spectral bands. **L1C** level processing builds upon L1B data with additional radiometric and geometric corrections. It involves converting radiance values to top-of-atmosphere (TOA) reflectance, refining geolocation using ground control points, ensuring uniform image resolution through orthorectification, and potentially transforming the image to a different map projection through reprojection. Finally, **L2** level processing transforms the L1C data into more advanced products. This typically involves correcting for atmospheric effects to convert reflectances from TOA to bottom-of-atmosphere (BOA), providing valuable insights for various applications.

Re-configurable data handling is crucial to prioritize data and products with varying latency needs, demanding efficient deployment frameworks in constrained processing environments. Insight4EO addresses these limitations, offering a comprehensive solution for onboard EO data processing.

The L1/L2 Product Generation module ensures real-time product generation from raw data, while the EO Applications module extracts insights through data prioritization and information retrieval. Data Services manage efficient data transfer, while Re-planning and Tasking enhance onboard autonomy. Insight4EO L1/L2 Product Generation for a Deimos-2 Multispectral Imager 17MP RGB image including Pixel Flagging, Equalization, Calibration, Denoising, Deconvolution, Cosmetic Filling and Restoration, Radiance to Reflectance, Band Alignment, Geolocation and Sea-Land Mask generation achieves processing latencies of less than 24 seconds on reference HW (Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC 4-core ARM Cortex A53); see Ta-

Figure 2: Overview of Insight4EO’s HW/SW and SW product.

Table 1: Processing times of the Insight4EO Optical L1/L2 Product, executed on the the Insight4EO Architecture.

Step	Time (seconds)
Radiometric Processing	
Pixel Flagging, Equalization, Calibration, Denoising, Deconvolution, Cosmetic Fill & Restoration, Radiance to Reflectance	19.2
Geometric Processing	
Band Alignment	1.8
Metadata Generation	
Geolocation	2.0
Sea-Land Mask	0.2
Total	23.3

ble 1. With Insight4EO and its ongoing capabilities development, the future of onboard EO data processing is promising, enabling faster, more effective satellite operations across various domains.

3 EO Applications for Disaster Management

Early detection of disasters is crucial for minimizing their impact and preventing catastrophic consequences. Hence, Insight4EO’s EO Applications module, designed to extract insights from the L1/L2 products, enabling real-time executions, is ideal to host disaster management applications.

As discussed in Section 2, the specified HW presents a challenge due to its limited computing capabilities. To address this limitation, the AI inference process, which is one of the most computationally intensive components of the processing chain, must be optimized for efficiency. This involves the trained AI model going through an optimization process aimed at reducing latency and enhancing performance. Initially, a custom DPU (Deep Learning Processing Unit) model is created to fully utilize the FPGA’s resources.

This is followed by a step of quantization-aware training, after which the model is quantized and calibrated using specific DPU parameters. Once quantization is completed, the model is compiled for the specific hardware architecture. The compiled model is then integrated into the target hardware to perform on-board AI inference with efficient latency, while maintaining the accuracy achieved during training.

Here we present two AI-based onboard satellite processed EO application examples for early warning of disasters: an application for extreme weather detection, developed for PERTEO [9], a persistent real-time earth observation satellite constellation for responsive disaster management, and an innovative application that extracts meaningful insights from SAR data using AI.

3.1 PERTEO: Extreme Weather Forecasting

Early detection of extreme weather conditions is a must to be able to reduce the impact of the future possible damage. PERTEO, a system comprising 48 instruments across 8 orbital planes and powered by Insight4EO’s onboard processing capabilities, addresses this challenge.

With a revisit latency of less than 1 hour for any payload and less than 3 hours for specific payload selections, PERTEO ensures swift disaster detection and management. Leveraging the Extreme Weather processing chain inherited from EO-ALERT [10], PERTEO enhances its capabilities with AI-based Extreme Weather detection. Utilizing a U-Net [11] like model, PERTEO identifies severe and non-severe clouds, distinguishing those with the potential to cause extreme convective weather events. This approach significantly enhances disaster detection efficiency, offering a proactive strategy to mitigate disasters and minimize their impact on affected regions. In Figure 3, visual results of the application are displayed.

Figure 3: Results of the Extreme Weather detection over SEVIRI data. a) Ground-truth Data; b) Classification obtained on ground; c) Insight4EO classification. Red: Severe events; green: Non-severe events.

3.2 AI for SAR Imagery: Disaster Detection

Unlike optical images, SAR imagery is not affected by cloud cover and darkness, and therefore actual revisit times will be closer to the naive geometric estimates, maintaining its performance levels during night and day. In addition to this capability, SAR is of particular relevance for maritime applications due to the high contrast it provides between water and land or floating objects. Additionally, SAR signals combined with AI are particularly interesting for disaster detection of floods and extreme weather conditions.

Considering that water bodies reflect SAR signals differently than land surfaces, appearing dark on SAR images due to the specular reflection of water, and the capabilities of ML/AI techniques, water surfaces can be identified and compared using water masks to save computational resources.

Comparing the current and the previously existing water bodies, floods can be detected. The areas where new water bodies are located can then be identified as flooded areas, which could be especially useful to identify the infrastructure that has been affected by the disaster.

As well as the Extreme Weather Forecasting mentioned in the previous subsection, SAR imagery can be used to this purpose as well. The intensity of the backscattered SAR signal varies with the roughness of the sea surface: smoother surfaces reflect less signal back to the SAR sensor, indicating lower wind speeds, whereas rougher surfaces with waves and ripples, caused by stronger winds, reflect more signal.

This capability of SAR to detect subtle variations in surface roughness allows for the accurate estimation of wind speed and direction, as shown in Figure 4. Applying ML techniques to this valuable information, weather forecasting could be performed to detect disasters.

Figure 4: Sea surface wind speed detected with SAR.

4 Results

The results of extreme weather detection application developed for PERTEO satellite are summarized in Table 2, where the Intersection over Union (IoU) and Dice scores for the cases of no-cloud, non-severe weather and severe weather forecasting, across training, validation, and on-device testing datasets are displayed.

The model is trained on images from Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) High Rate Spinning Enhanced Visible and Infrared Imager (SEVIRI), a dataset of 8,358 images with 2,289,822 potential convective cells from 164 days with high weather activity in 2016, 2017, and 2018. The labels are obtained from the OPERA weather radar network. The model is optimized and compiled for the Insight4EO platform using the VITIS-AI framework.

The image processing on the Insight4EO hardware takes about 1.2 seconds per image, covering an area of 6.855.192 km² over Europe. Based on the communication results from EO-ALERT, we estimate a total

latency of less than 1.5 minutes for product delivery. The whole process involves image generation, image processing, and product generation, providing solutions and insights for early Extreme Weather detection and assessment.

Dataset	Class	IoU	Dice
Train	No cloud	96.16	98.04
	Non-severe	51.18	67.70
	Severe	64.28	78.26
Validation	No cloud	95.88	97.89
	Non-severe	45.24	62.30
	Severe	51.71	68.17
Test (on device)	No cloud	95.28	97.58
	Non-severe	37.33	54.36
	Severe	36.28	53.24

Table 2: Extreme Weather detection performance

5 Discussion

This work has presented Insight4EO, available as an integrated HW/SW solution and/or standalone SW, that supports onboard AI multiapplications for EO from the end-user. Insight4EO offers a range of application SW functionalities, including the efficient generation of EO L1/L2 products directly onboard satellites. It also includes a suite of pre-built AI EO applications for immediate use, as well as support for custom AI applications developed by end-users. Moreover, Insight4EO manages data processing with features such as encryption, compression, and adaptable data handling methods, and it enhances onboard autonomy by providing re-planning and tasking capabilities, enabling satellites to autonomously adapt and respond to changing conditions.

The capabilities of the EO Applications module of Insight4EO have also been presented, offering low-latency algorithms, invaluable for early warning of disasters and disaster management, and the versatility to support both optical and SAR payloads.

Acknowledgements. The research leading to this publication has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776311 (EO-ALERT).

DEIMOS would like to acknowledge the European Space Agency (ESA) InCubed programme for their support in the development of Insight4EO, and also express our gratitude to the Spanish State Meteorological Agency (AEMET) and EUMETSAT for the data supporting EO-ALERT.

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